

HYPERTHYROIDISM

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Abstract

Endocrinological diseases caused by changes in the regulation of thyroid hormones are spreading rapidly over time in the world, and develop with many known consequences, namely, other diseases, which complicate the process of diagnosing and treating patients with hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism. This paper is devoted to an overview of the second disease: definition, symptoms, possible complications and ways to identify and control it.

Keywords: hyperthyroidism, thyroiditis, hormones, thyroid gland, symptoms, diagnosis.

Hyperthyroidism is a condition of the thyroid gland in which the amount of hormones produced increases, characterized by a latent or overt course. If the TSH level is reduced, it becomes a thyroid cause of the disease.

Overt hyperthyroidism is a combination of symptoms caused by an excessive amount of thyroid hormones, in which there is an increased concentration of free fractions in the blood.

In latent hyperthyroidism, the symptoms are subtle, but only a reduced TSH level can indicate the presence of deviant thyroid behavior.

A type of hyperthyroidism in which the clinical symptoms and thyroid hormones are of exogenous origin or synthesized outside the thyroid gland is called thyrotoxicosis.

Subjective symptoms:

1. Nervous system and mental state:

- anxiety;
- insomnia;
- poor concentration;
- irritability;
- similar symptoms in bipolar disorder and schizophrenia;

2. Skin:

- sweating;
- hair loss;
- flushing;

3. Muscles:

- weakness;
- fatigue;

4. Cardiovascular system:

- arrhythmia;
- increased heart rate;
- heart failure;

5. Respiratory system:

- shortness of breath;

6. Digestive system:

- diarrhea;
- increased and decreased appetite;

7. Urinary system:

- mild polyuria;

8. Reproductive system:

- in women - menstrual irregularities;

- in men - erectile dysfunction.

Objective symptoms:

1. Nervous system;

- tremors of the hands, tongue or eyeballs;
- increased tendon reflexes;

2. Eyes:

- eyelid retraction;
- Greffe's symptoms;
- Kocher's symptoms;
- Möbius symptoms;
- Stelvag's symptoms;

3. Skin:

- warm, pink, moist, excessively smooth;
- sometimes hyperpigmentation of the mucous membranes;

- urticaria;

- gynecomastia in men;

- hair loss;

- brittle nails, onycholysis;

4. Muscles:

- decrease in muscle volume and strength;
- muscle atrophy;
- ptosis, diplopia;

5. Cardiovascular system:

- tachycardia;
- systolic hypertension;
- increased blood pressure amplitude;
- irregular cardiac activity;
- mesosystolic or presystolic murmur;
- heart failure;
- atrial fibrillation;
- coronary heart disease;

6. Digestive system:

- rarely liver enlargement;
- jaundice;

7. Goiter.

Hyperthyroidism is an abnormal behavior of the thyroid gland, which produces an increased amount of thyroid hormones. In the United States, the disease affects 1.2% of the population. Hyperthyroidism occurs due to various causes: Graves' disease, toxic adenomas, and multinodular goiter. The diagnosis is based on clinical data, ultrasound, radioiodine uptake scan, and biochemical tests.

One of the most common causes of hyperthyroidism is Graves' disease, followed by toxic adenomas and multinodular goiter. A goiter is an autoimmune disease that develops due to a lack of immunotolerance, as it causes the formation of antibodies to thyrotropin receptors, which in turn bind to thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) receptors. This increases the level of thyroid hormones. Hypothyroidism also occurs due to non-toxic nodular goiters.

Other causes of hyperthyroidism are ovarian contusion, thyroid cancer, germ cell and trophoblastic tumors, iodine-infected pituitary tumors, silent, painful, painless thyroiditis, or amiodarone-induced thyroiditis.

During pregnancy, overt hyperthyroidism may occur, or subacute thyroiditis during the postpartum period. This type of thyrotoxicosis is characterized by hyperthyroidism and restoration of thyroid regulation. Therefore, antithyroid drugs and radioactive iodine are not useful during treatment.

During subsequent pregnancies, relapses of postpartum and painless thyroiditis may develop, and therefore constant monitoring of such patients is recommended. Infections can cause painful thyroiditis, which will resolve on its own. Treatment should be with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs or steroids in severe conditions and beta-blockers if symptoms of any thyrotoxicosis are seen.

Thyroiditis developed due to amiodarone can be of the first and second types. The first type develops due to the underlying disease of a DTC or GP, which reacts to the high concentration of iodine in amiodarone, thus increasing the amount of hormones produced by the thyroid gland. Treatment is necessary with potassium perchlorate or antithyroid drugs. The second is known as destructive thyroiditis, which occurs as a result of the toxic effects of amiodarone. In this case, treatment is required with surgery or steroids.

Various body systems react to this condition: skin, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, immune, and reproductive systems. It is necessary to recognize the symptoms of the cardiovascular part of the body in time, such as hypertension and tachycardia, with beta-blockers to prevent further deterioration of this system and the disease in general, and in this case, it is necessary to treat

it with radioactive iodine, an antithyroid drug or with surgery.

A comprehensive assessment of the psychopathological state of people with hyperthyroidism shows that the disease is expressed by irritable, anxious, emotionally labile, and negative mood. Compared to hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism has a much higher incidence of aggression among patients, but the feelings of guilt and resentment are the same. Indeed, as the amount of thyroid hormones increases, the level of aggressiveness and impulsivity increases significantly. Patients with this disease are characterized by "interpersonal sensitivity" and "hostility". Also, psychoendocrine syndrome in hyperthyroidism is expressed by a manic state that occurs due to thyroid hormones.

The diagnosis of the disease is determined by a decrease in TSH concentration and an increase in FT4 or, rarely, FT3 levels, which may indicate manifest hyperthyroidism, even if the symptoms are subtle. The steps to diagnose subclinical and secondary hyperthyroidism are slightly different because in these types of disease, TSH levels are normal or elevated.

Hyperthyroidism is one of the most complex endocrinological pathological diseases that requires several types of diagnostics to choose the right treatment, taking into account the decisions of the patient and the doctor. Research confirms that there are successful cases of the process of combating this disease, but there are still gaps in scientific works, so observations are ongoing, most importantly, an optimistic attitude can solve problems, but it takes time.

References

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